

CULTURAL RELATIONS BETWEEN THE KOKAND KHANATE AND THE PEOPLES OF XINJIANG IN THE MID-18TH TO 19TH CENTURIES

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Abstract:

This article analyzes the cultural relations between the Kokand Khanate and the peoples of Xinjiang in the mid-18th to 19th centuries. The study highlights the cultural proximity that developed on the basis of socio-political and economic interactions between the two regions, with particular attention to mutual influences in applied arts, architecture, music, cuisine, and literature. It also examines the impact of migration processes and scholarly-literary connections on cultural development. The results of the analysis show that the cultural relations between the Kokand Khanate and Xinjiang were a natural and organic process, contributing to the formation of a shared cultural heritage between the two peoples.

Keywords: Kokand Khanate, Xinjiang, cultural relations, Uyghurs, Uzbeks, applied arts, maqom, literature, craftsmanship, Silk Road, migration, cultural heritage.

INTRODUCTION

Central Asia, including the peoples of Xinjiang—such as the Uyghurs, Uzbeks, Kyrgyz, Kazakhs, Turkmens, Tajiks, and Karakalpaks—who came under the rule of the Qing Dynasty in 1759, maintained close relations with one another. In particular, during the 18th–19th centuries, in the period of the Kokand Khanate (1709–1876), these relations intensified, and processes of cultural integration between the peoples of the two regions accelerated. Similarities in language, customs, arts, and literature between the Uyghur and Uzbek peoples are considered to be the result of these interactions.

The aim of this study is to analyze the main directions of cultural relations between the Kokand Khanate and the peoples of Xinjiang in the 18th–19th centuries, as well as their impact on socio-cultural life.

METHODS

The following methods were used in the study:

- Historical-analytical method – studying the development of cultural relations based on sources;

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- Comparative analysis – identifying similarities and differences between the cultures of the two regions;
- Source studies approach – analyzing literary, ethnographic, and historical data;
- Systematic approach – examining cultural relations in connection with socio-political and economic processes.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The socio-political, ethno-demographic processes and economic relations between the Kokand Khanate and the peoples of Xinjiang also had a significant impact on the spiritual and cultural life of both regions, as well as on the development of arts, science, and literature. There were numerous common features in their way of life and customs. Many examples can be provided that demonstrate the rich cultural ties and shared characteristics between these two Turkic peoples (Yudakhin K., 1958:31).

Cultural Relations in the Field of Traditional Culture and Arts of the Uzbek and Uyghur Peoples

The settlement of Uyghurs in the territory of Central Asia dates back to ancient times. For many centuries, the Uzbek and Uyghur peoples were connected through the Great Silk Road. While the Uzbek people were actively engaged along the western routes of the Great Silk Road located on the western side of the Pamir and the Tien Shan (Chinese: Tian Shan), the Uyghurs were particularly active along the trade routes on the eastern side of these mountains.

It is known that the regions on both sides of these mountains were among the most ancient cultural centers of Asia. This is confirmed by archaeological findings discovered in Mawarannahr and the Tarim Basin. According to these findings, continuous interactions between the populations of both regions persisted without interruption. During the periods of the Turkic Khaganate and the Karakhanid state, these territories were within a single political entity. During the reign of Amir Timur, their mutual relations along the Great Silk Road became even more active. For this reason, the areas inhabited by the Uyghurs are not limited only to the territory of Xinjiang. The closeness of the Uyghur and Uzbek languages, as well as similarities in customs and musical traditions, serve as evidence of this connection.

The arrival and settlement of migrants in the Khanate led to exchanges of skills and methods in cultural life between migrants and the local population. In particular, interactions between the people of Xinjiang and the inhabitants of the Khanate in areas such as house construction techniques, production of clothing, musical instruments, jewelry making, pottery, and metal engraving contributed significantly to the development of these crafts through the exchange of experience. Under the influence of migrant artisans from Xinjiang, craftsmen of the Khanate began producing new items in “Kashgar-style” and “Uyghur-style.”

Blacksmiths and coppersmiths of Fergana and Xinjiang decorated metal utensils such as copper jugs, trays, and teapots with traditional lattice-like ornamental patterns on their lids, handles, upper and lower parts. Producing such finely decorated items required high craftsmanship and refined artistic taste from metal engravers. Such items are widely found in the collections of craftsmen in both Fergana and Xinjiang (Abdullaev., 1974:20). In many cases, Kashgar-style copper jugs decorated in this manner were brought from Xinjiang to the markets of the Kokand Khanate for sale (Kuropatkin., 1879:63). At the same time, artisans of the Khanate also adopted these Kashgar decorative techniques from migrant Xinjiang craftsmen. The jugs produced in this

style by the Khanate's artisans became known as "Kashgar-style jugs." These jugs were smaller than those produced traditionally in the Khanate, with rounded bodies, sometimes decorated and sometimes plain (Nozilov., 1992:78).

Craftsmen engaged in copper processing in the Khanate also produced copper trays decorated with cloud-like patterns commonly found in Chinese visual art, influenced by Xinjiang artisans (Abdullaev., 1974:37). In the 19th century, several migrant Xinjiang metal engravers were active among the Kokand craftsmen. Among them, an artisan named Musavvir Kashgari was well known among the people (Bulatov., 1992:282). One of the applied arts that mutually enriched both the Kokand Khanate and Xinjiang craftsmanship was jewelry making. This is because these regions were rich in natural resources necessary for the development of jewelry—gold, silver, and precious stones. These materials were used by Xinjiang jewelers as well, who produced their goods using raw materials, including gold, brought from the Kokand Khanate (Bobobekov., 1996:102). Silver, jade, emeralds, and diamonds were found in the mountains near Khotan. These resources were purchased by merchants of the Khanate, who gained considerable profit from them (Soguchi., 1963:67).

In addition, these merchants supplied turquoise, rubies, corals, and other precious stones from Badakhshan and Ladakh to the jewelers of Kokand and Xinjiang. This, in turn, led to the development of mutual relations between the jewelers of the two regions.

Kashgar jewelers who migrated to the Kokand Khanate continued practicing their craft there as well. The jewelry pieces they produced became famous not only among the population of the Khanate but throughout Central Asia. Such jewelry items were known as "Kashgar baldok," "Kashgar-style earrings (isirga)," and "Kashgar-style earrings (zirak)" (Karimova., 2005:85). The crescent-shaped "Kashgar-style isirga" was decorated with beads and silver pendants. The technique of making the "Kashgar baldok" by Kashgar jewelers was similar to that of Kokand jewelers. This ring was crafted from gold and silver in a circular form, with delicate floral wire lattice patterns extending from the lower to the upper part, filled in the center with tiny granules (or small pearls) forming floral motifs. It was sometimes further enriched with turquoise stones shaped like an eye or with leaf-shaped gold ornaments. The lattice-like floral design at the lower part of the ring was made in the form of a new crescent moon. The elegant shape, delicate lattice ornamentation, the shine of gold and pearls, and the refined craftsmanship gave this ornament a special charm (Qashqarbaldok., 2005:631).

Among the Uyghur jewelers living in Kokand in the 19th century, a Kashgar craftsman named Mahmud was particularly skilled in producing such ornaments. He was also well known for his tasteful decoration of trays and teaware. In the 19th century, the number of migrant Kashgar jewelers living in Kokand exceeded 50 (Umarov A., Umarova Z., 2004:175).

At the beginning of the 19th century, Rishtan pottery was renowned not only in the Fergana Valley but throughout Central Asia. The connections between the Kokand Khanate and Xinjiang are also evident in the works of Rishtan potters. In the early 19th century, one of the Rishtan potters, Usto Jalil, traveled to Xinjiang for trade and learned from local potters the techniques of producing large glazed storage jars (hum) and decorating ceramic vessels in "Kashgar-style" and "Chinese-style" (Peshcherova., 1958:229). Soon, these techniques became widespread among Rishtan potters. They began producing ceramics resembling Chinese celadon porcelain. These ceramic items had surfaces glazed in turquoise and white, decorated with fine patterns in blue and dark red colors (Nozilova., 1992:64). The ornaments often depicted green vegetation motifs. These ceramic items were valued as ceremonial objects and were used at weddings and festive events. Such pottery products made by Rishtan craftsmen were also exported and sold in the markets of Xinjiang.

Khotan and Yarkand carpets were famous not only in Central Asia but also in countries such as Afghanistan, Iran, the Arab states, India, and China. These carpets were valued on the world market at prices comparable to the renowned Persian carpets of their time (Karimova., 1987:146). In Xinjiang, the inhabitants of several villages were engaged in carpet weaving. These carpets were mainly woven from high-quality, fine sheep wool; in addition, carpets were also made from silk and cotton.

Khotan carpets were woven with various plant-like motifs and scenic patterns depicting animals. Xinjiang weavers used more than ten colors in the process of weaving each carpet. This rich color combination created new visual compositions. As Felkzem wrote, these carpets stood out not only for the wealth of the local population but also for their external appearance: “Such beautiful colorfulness is not found in Central Asian carpets” (Felkzem., 1914:152).

Carpets and felt products woven from cotton in Khotan, Yarkand, and Aksu were famous in Central Asian markets for their softness and delicacy. A. Kun recognized Yarkand carpets as one of the important goods transported from Xinjiang to the Kokand Khanate (Kun., 1873:114). Moreover, as a result of the experience brought by migrant craftsmen, the weaving of such carpets also became widespread in the Kokand Khanate. According to Ch. Valikhanov, carpets woven by Xinjiang craftsmen in Margilan were decorated with Chinese patterns (Valikhanov., 1987:201). Among the weavers of the Khanate, it became common to produce “Kashgar-style” carpets featuring plant and fruit tree motifs at the center (Moshkova., 1970:96–97). White felt brought from Kashgar was considered of the highest quality, and local rulers were seated on it and elevated to the throne (Yujin Skyler., 2019:138).

Since these two regions were located on the slopes of the Tien Shan mountain ranges, they were naturally and geographically similar. This similarity influenced the main occupations, lifestyle, clothing, food, housing, and socio-economic conditions of their populations, which did not differ significantly from one another. In particular, similarities were reflected in house construction, especially in the naming of rooms, as well as in their artistic decoration and furnishing. The population of the Khanate also adopted “Kashgar-style” architectural elements from migrants who arrived from Xinjiang (Voronina., 1940:62).

One such element was the “Kashgar-style chimney-hearth,” which had a triangular front wall with a flat top and an open part shaped like a simple arch (Nozilov., 1992:29–30). These chimneys, known among the population of the Khanate as “Kashgar-style chimneys,” became widespread in the homes of the local population of the Fergana Valley by the 19th–20th centuries (Pisarchik., 1982:88). Xinjiang craftsmen also actively participated in the construction of the Khudoyar Khan palace (1872), where the chimneys were built in the “Kashgar-style” (Ahmedov., 1995:85).

The heated rooms of the palace with “Kashgar-style chimneys” were covered with wooden planks (parquet) arranged in a decorative manner. In addition, the “Kashgar-style veranda” also became widespread in the Fergana Valley and the Tashkent oasis (Voronina., 1949:73). The “Kashgar-style veranda,” or ravn, was a raised veranda surrounded by windows and lattice structures (Zohidov., 1996:66).

At the same time, it is known that migrant populations from the Kokand Khanate also adopted certain features of architectural culture. For example, among Uyghurs living in Xinjiang, it was not customary to divide the courtyard into “inner” (ichkari) and “outer” (tashkari) parts. However, some Uyghurs who began living together with Uzbeks and Tajiks in the Khanate started to build separate inner and outer sections in their homes, which was undoubtedly influenced by the Kokand population (Abdullaev., 2005:84). The study of specialized academic literature shows that

many Uyghurs living in Xinjiang, particularly in Kashgar, used chimney-hearth systems similar to those of the settled population of the Fergana Valley, and these structures were almost identical in design (Pevtsov., 1949:114).

In residential architecture, the interaction between Fergana and Kashgar traditions created a unique harmony. In the processing and decoration of wooden elements such as ceilings, columns, and building structures, the applied arts of the two regions blended together while preserving their distinctive characteristics.

Uyghur historian Yusuf Ziya Shirvani writes about the culture of Xinjiang as follows: “Xinjiang lies on the trade route connecting the West to Asia. Therefore, even in ancient times, Xinjiang became a transit zone—a center of art, crafts, and culture, as well as a place of exchange. This situation contributed to the growth of Xinjiang’s culture. As a result, Xinjiang came to possess a rich and distinctive cultural heritage” (Yusuf Ziya Shervoniy., 1947:10).

Uyghur maqoms differ from Uzbek maqoms not only in their number (twelve instead of six), but also in their richness, liveliness, melodic diversity, and the variety of performances (Khudjamaro v., 1962:75). The “Twelve Muqam” occupies the highest and most prestigious place in the spiritual life of the Uyghur people. It is characterized by its exceptional artistic refinement, profound content, and its comprehensive reflection of life and natural phenomena. At the same time, it serves as an expression of the national characteristics and traditions of the Uyghur people in music. In the Twelve Muqam, the four seasons of the year, the distinct features and qualities of each season, and the unique characteristics of the twelve months are masterfully depicted. Certain sections such as “Roh” and “Mushovarak” have been incorporated into the Uzbek maqom tradition and are referred to by Uzbek performers as “Kashgar-style Roh” and “Mushovarak maqoms.” This indicates that the interactions between the two regions contributed to the development of the musical culture of their populations.

The types and characteristics of food among the peoples of the Kokand Khanate and Xinjiang were determined, on the one hand, by natural conditions and economic activities, and on the other hand, by the specific cultural features of local ethnic groups. For example, the cuisine of populations engaged in ancient agriculture and craftsmanship differed from that of pastoral groups originating from semi-nomadic steppe regions. At the same time, the dishes of migrant Xinjiang peoples enriched the cuisine of the Khanate, introducing foods such as manti, laghman, manpar, and others. Among both Uzbek and Uyghur cuisines, dough-based dishes occupy a special place. The word manti originates from Chinese, meaning “round dough,” while laghman, from Dungan, means “long or stretched dough” (Jabbarov., 1994:166).

Although Uzbek and Uyghur dishes have come to share many similarities, their names sometimes differ. For example: moshkichir–moshova, shula–shovla, chöchira–chuchvara, khuda–mastava. Among the Uyghur people, dishes are also described in various symbolic ways: pilaf—a dish for guests, laghman—a dish of affection, manti—a dish for men, ugra—a dish for rest, halva—a dish for children, kebab—a dish of trade, and norin—a dish for the generous.

Tea consumption was widespread in Central Asia, including among the populations of the Kokand Khanate and Xinjiang (Mahmudov., 1987:53; Khojaev A., 2008:106). In 1762, the Chinese emperor Qianlong sent tea and atlas silk as a gift to the ruler of Kokand (Kuznetsov., 1983:56). In the Khanate, tea was consumed with milk, cream, salt, sheep fat, quince, grapes, almonds, and even flour (Abashin., 2001:62–90). Uyghurs also valued tea as a healing drink. Among them, several methods of tea preparation were known. For example, tea called “Aytqon tea” was prepared in a special way by boiling milk, black tea, and cream together. This type of tea was especially consumed by the inhabitants of Ghulja. In Kashgar, green tea was mixed with milk and consumed.

Important Aspects of Scientific and Literary Relations

Eastern culture, including the scientific and literary centers of Central Asia, did not develop without cooperation and mutual intellectual exchange. In turn, every creator and Eastern thinker working within these traditions could not enter the world of science and literature without being influenced by the schools of prominent representatives of Islamic and Sufi thought such as Abulqosim Firdavsiy, Sa'diy Sheroziy, Alisher Navoiy, Mirzo Bedil, Fuzuliy, and other masters of literature. The creators of scientific and literary centers in the Kokand Khanate and Xinjiang in the 18th–19th centuries were no exception.

The literary relations between Central Asia and Xinjiang, including between the Uzbek and Uyghur peoples, developed naturally. These two regions, which had historically existed within unified states, shared common language, religion, and similar ethnic traditions. Their populations frequently interacted and moved between regions. In particular, scholars and literary figures actively participated in cultural processes in both areas. Historical sources provide numerous examples confirming this. Secondly, as political, social, and economic relations developed, cultural ties and mutual influence in science and literature intensified. Thirdly, works created by authors in one region were supplemented and enriched by scholars and writers in the other, leading to mutual creative influence.

For instance, the Namangan-born Boborahim Mashrab lived in Xinjiang, and his poetry became widespread among Uyghur literary scholars and musicians. In turn, the works of the Xinjiang poet Sheikh Zaliliy Kashgari attracted the attention of 19th-century Kokand poets. The unique tone and charm of his ghazals helped to fully reveal their deep mystical essence (Juraboev., 2008:80–94). Perhaps for this reason, the Kokand ruler and talented poet Amir Umarxon composed takhmis on three of Zaliliy Kashgari's ghazals, while later another Kokand literary figure, Mirmakhmud Qori Khokandiy (1828–1906), composed takhmis on five of his ghazals. (In the *Devon of Amiriy* published in the 1970s, a takhmis on Zaliliy's ghazal with the radif "Bor" was included (Amiriy., 1972:344–345)).

During the 15th–16th centuries, the spread of Islam in Xinjiang intensified. Representatives of Sufi orders, poets, and scholars from Central Asia, especially from Bukhara, increasingly entered the region. In particular, after the death of Mahdumi A'zam, the arrival and settlement of his sons Khoja Ishaq and Khoja Kalon in Kashgar and Yarkand contributed to the wide dissemination of Sufi ideas. By the late 17th century, the activities of Mahdumi A'zam's grandson Afaq Khoja in Xinjiang led to the emergence of genres of mystical poetry and literature. The teaching of the works of great figures such as Rudakiy, Nizomiy Ganjaviiy, Abdurahmon Jomiy, and Alisher Navoiy in the madrasas of Kashgar, Khotan, and Yarkand had a positive influence on the творчество of Uyghur poets and writers of that period (Mamatokhunov., 1960:11).

In the Kokand Khanate, there was also great interest in the works of Xinjiang poets and writers. Alongside the works of major Eastern literary figures such as Fuzuliy, Abdurahmon Jomiy, Lutfiy, Alisher Navoiy, and Boborahim Mashrab, the population also widely read the ghazals of Uyghur writers such as Muhammad Sodiq Kashgari, Arshiy (real name Khoja Jahan Khoja Yaqub), Zaliliy, as well as Muhammad Siddiq Rushdiy, Hislat Kashgari, Hushhol Gharibi, and Oraziy. In the madrasas and schools of the Khanate, Muhammad Sodiq Kashgari's work "Odob us-solihin" ("The Ethics of the Righteous") was taught as a textbook (Qayumov., 1965:52).

Shared cultural heritage serves as a mirror of the long-standing relations between closely connected peoples. At the same time, it is one of the main sources demonstrating how inseparably intertwined their past histories are. This can be clearly seen in the example of the literary legacy of

Boborahim Mashrab. His works became part of the spiritual wealth of both Uzbek and Uyghur peoples. In particular, the “Mashrab gatherings,” which have become a part of Uyghur literary creativity and oral tradition and have been preserved to this day, serve as a vivid example of this shared heritage.

Boborahim Mashrab creatively drew upon examples of Uyghur folk songs in composing his works, and his contribution was highly appreciated by representatives of the literary environment of Xinjiang. Boborahim Mashrab also harmonized the cultural achievements of the two regions in the practice of Sufi rituals. In particular, within the Uyghur pir–murshid (spiritual guide) tradition, he contributed to shaping the khanaqah dance (ritual method), drawing on the sama practice. Specifically, when Sufi leaders (eshon–sufis) performed zikr with their disciples, a singer (hafiz, also called halfa) would stand among them or on a platform and perform Sufi-themed chants, while the others engaged in zikr accompanied by rhythmic movements and dance adapted to these melodies.

Mashrab drew inspiration from the melodies of the Uyghur Twelve Muqam and made effective use of them in his творчество. He set his poems to the musical structures of the Twelve Muqam (Shklovsky., 1987:151–155). Even today, compositions based on the poet’s works continue to be performed by the people of Xinjiang. Mashrab’s творчество influenced not only the religious and Sufi beliefs of the Xinjiang population but also the traditional Uyghur folk dances and songs that have been performed there since ancient times.

At the same time, Mashrab’s works became deeply integrated into the literary tradition of the Xinjiang peoples. It is not difficult to demonstrate both his influence by Uyghur oral folklore and his impact on their literary heritage. For example, when the Uyghur folk song “Deyman” is compared with Mashrab’s ghazal “Derman,” it becomes evident that they are nearly identical both in content and in form Mashrab:

Ul dilrabo ra’noga men yor bo‘lay derman,
 May bersa xaridori bir qatra totay derman.
 (I say I would become a lover to that charming beauty,
 If offered wine, I would taste even a single drop.)

Uyghur folk song:

Oltun bilan ra’noni,
 Yorimga tutay deyman,
 May bersa, xaridorim,
 Bir qatra totay deyman.
 (I say I would offer gold and beauty to my beloved,
 If given wine, I would taste even a single drop.)

Likewise, the texts of the Uyghur Twelve Muqam and songs considered examples of Uyghur poetic creativity—such as “Yurak muntazir” and “Arzimni aytay”—are similar in content, language, and style to Mashrab’s ghazals like “Ko‘rsat jamoling,” “Devona bo‘ldum,” and “Arzimni aytay.”

Mashrab’s poems spread widely among the people of Xinjiang. Under the influence of his literary legacy, Uyghur poets and writers such as Saydulla ibn Hoji Yusuf, Hirqatiy, Khorobotiy, Bilol Nozim, and Nazariy created their own artistic works.

At the beginning of the 18th century, during the reign of the Yarkand ruler Khoja Jahan Khoja Yaqub (1736–1756), certain changes occurred in the cultural life of the state. During his rule, conflicts with Dzungaria ceased, and a peaceful life was established (Malloudov., 1990:5–6). The ruler himself made a significant contribution to the development of Xinjiang’s cultural life.

According to 18th–19th century Uyghur sources, “Khoja Jahan Khoja Yaqub was the eldest son of Daniyal Khoja, the grandson of Shu‘ayb from the ‘Qarataghlik’ lineage, and was born in Khujand in 1685” (Mullo Muso Sayromiy., 1986:142).

Between 1690 and 1722, he studied in madrasas of Central Asian cities such as Khujand, Bukhara, Kokand, and Samarkand (Khoja Jahan Arshiy., 1995:3). He gained fame by participating in literary and scholarly gatherings of scholars and poets in Bukhara and Samarkand. Writing under the pen name Arshiy, he composed poetry in Arabic, Persian, and Turkic languages (Khoja Jahan Arshiy., 1995:6). Today, manuscripts of his works are preserved in the manuscript collection of the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Republic of Tajikistan and in the Xinjiang State Literature Museum in China.

After ascending the throne of Yarkand in 1736, he patronized various fields of cultural development in Xinjiang and sponsored the construction of madrasas and schools. Arshiy regularly taught at the Golden Madrasa of Yarkand every Thursday. Historical sources note that students from Central Asia, including from the Kokand Khanate, studied at this madrasa (Niyoz Karimiy., 2004:178).

It is also important to note that prominent representatives of classical literature such as Khomush Yarkandiy, Muhammad Temur Kashgari, Muhammad Siddiq Rushdiy, Muhammad Sodiq Kashgari, Mir Fazil Navbatiy, Shahmuhammad ibn Nizomiddin, Khorobotiy, Zaliliy, and others lived and created during this period. Muhammad Sodiq Kashgari compared Arshiy’s reign to that of Sultan Husayn Bayqara (Khoja Jahan Arshiy., 1995:6). His son Sodiq Khoja Futuhiy also followed the tradition of Alisher Navoi and composed poetry.

During the reign of Khoja Jahan Khoja Yaqub, a distinctive school of calligraphy developed in the region. Many famous literary and historical works—such as “Tazkirai Bughrakhon,” “Rawzat us-safo,” and the divans of Alisher Navoi, Abdurahmon Jami, Komil Khorezmi, and Mirzo Abdulqodir Bedil—were copied by calligraphers. This had a significant impact on the development of literary processes in the region (Mukhlisov., 1973:43).

Under the leadership of Mirza Muhammad Nazar, Xinjiang calligraphers copied works of Alisher Navoi such as “Hazoyin ul-maoniy” and “Mahbub ul-qulub,” while Mullo Sarimsoq Khoqandiy transcribed his “Hayrat ul-abror” and “Tarikh-i mulki ajam” in the nasta‘liq style and presented them to readers (Akbarov., 2004:281).

Only a single divan of ghazals written in 1740 by the Khotan poet Navbatiy has survived to the present day. In his творчество, the strong influence of Alisher Navoiy is clearly evident (Mamatokhunov., 1960:12). However, when Burhaniddin Khoja, a claimant to the throne of the Yarkand Khanate, together with his brother Khoja Jahan, captured Yarkand in 1756, Khoja Jahan Khoja Yaqub was deposed and executed along with his family. The literary circle he had created dispersed in different directions.

One of them was Muhammad Siddiq Rushdiy of Yarkand, who, in the second half of the 18th century, followed his patron Khoja Kafakbek—an influential political figure in Xinjiang—to the court of Kokand ruler Erdonabiy (Ostonakulov., 2002:55–56). There, under the patronage and at the request of Khoja Kafakbek, he composed a major work about Sufi saints. This work, titled “Tazkirat ul-awliyo,” is considered the second major tazkira written in Turkic after Alisher Navoiy and contains accounts of the lives of ninety-five sheikhs. It was completed in 1780.

As a result of the development of cultural relations between Xinjiang and the Kokand Khanate, the art of calligraphy also flourished. For more than five centuries, a special school of calligraphy emerged in Xinjiang, where Uyghur scholars copied the works of Alisher Navoiy and other Turkic authors. This community, which considered preserving, copying, and disseminating

Navoi's works a duty and a virtuous act, became known in Central Asia as the "Kashgar Calligraphy School." Especially during the Yarkand Khanate period, the reading, copying, and compilation of Navoi's works reached a high level of development.

The "Khanate Chancellery" (court office), established during the reign of Abdurashid Khan, became an important center for publishing and distributing Navoi's works. "From the 16th century onward, Navoi studies took deep root in cities of Xinjiang such as Kashgar, Khotan, Aksu, and Kucha. Two months after Navoi's death, his 'Chor Devon' was fully copied in the madrasa of Kucha. In 1700, this divan was copied again under the title 'Khazoyin ul-maoniy.' A third manuscript copy of this work was prepared in the same period in the city of Kumul by a man named Mullo Maqsud" (Qodiriy., 1980:11).

According to linguistic and social research conducted across Xinjiang between 1950 and 1957, initially 400 manuscript copies of Navoi's works were discovered and studied. Later, among 700 manuscripts examined, 150 were identified as belonging to Navoi himself (Turkash., 1998:49).

In addition to preserving manuscripts of Navoi's works, Xinjiang calligraphers inscribed his wise verses in gold lettering on mausoleums, on the walls and columns of madrasas and schools, and engraved them on metal and copper objects. For instance, in 1955, in the Karakash district of Khotan, a decorated ewer was discovered bearing a ghazal beginning with the line "Ne noma erdiki, g'amgin ko'ngilni shod etting," and it was determined that this object had been crafted in 1842 (Usmon., 1992:307).

Works such as "Bakhtiyornoma," "Tazkirai avliyo," "Me'rojnoma," as well as the "Muhabbatnoma" of the Uzbek classical poet Komil Khorezmi were copied in large numbers between 1800–1810 by Uyghur calligraphers, including Abdurahim Nazariy of Kashgar and Gharibiy Ziyoiy. This, too, was a result of mutual literary relations (Qodiriy., 1966:20). According to the researcher Kh. Solihova, in general, during the 18th–19th centuries, the art of calligraphy developed significantly in Kashgar and Yarkand, and many works of Alisher Navoiy were copied by calligraphers (Solihova., 1995:42–44). Some of these manuscripts bore the original titles of the poet's works, while others were titled "Kulliyot" (Complete Collection), "Bayoz" (Selected Collection), or "Devon" (Collection of Poems).

During this period, the fame of calligraphers bearing the pen name "Kashgari" and the manuscripts they copied spread from Xinjiang to Central Asia, Tatarstan, and Azerbaijan. Today, in the manuscript collection of the Abu Rayhan Beruni Institute of Oriental Studies of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, more than 450 manuscript and printed works of Alisher Navoiy are preserved, copied by nearly 150 calligraphers. Among 66 identified manuscripts, six were produced by authors using the pen name "Kashgari." Among the works preserved in this collection, a "Kulliyot" of Navoi's works was copied and compiled in Kashgar between 1824–1830 by a calligrapher named Abdurahim Fazil Kashgari. This collection includes 19 of Navoi's works and is considered one of the most valuable manuscripts in terms of its scope, calligraphic artistry, and scholarly significance.

The governor of Kashgar, Zuhuriddin Khoja (1832–1835), also patronized poets and writers from both Xinjiang and the Kokand Khanate. During this period, the tradition of khamsa-writing (hamsanavislik) continued among the Uyghurs. This tradition had two main purposes: first, to copy and disseminate Khamsa of Alisher Navoi, and second, to compose nazira (creative responses) to its epics. During the reign of Zuhuriddin Khoja, Navoi's Khamsa was copied in 500 copies (Mukhlisov., 1973:66). Even today, various manuscript versions of the Khamsa are preserved in Xinjiang; for example, 21 copies are kept in the Kashgar regional museum.

Furthermore, according to the catalog “Manuscripts of Alisher Navoi’s Khamsa,” among 170 copies preserved in the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan and the Hamid Suleimanov Manuscript Fund, 12 were copied by Xinjiang calligraphers. The Uyghur calligrapher Umar Boqi, in 1792, rewrote the epics “Farhod va Shirin” and “Layli va Majnun” in a simple and understandable prose style. These were later published in Tashkent in lithographic editions in 1909, 1910, 1912, and 1915 under the titles “Qissayi Farhod-Shirin” and “Kitobi Layli-Majnun.” The first epic contained 13 miniatures, and the second 11 miniatures (Hakimov., 1992:248).

In 1813, Mullo Siddiq also rendered four epics from the Khamsa into prose, adding “Lison ut-tayr,” and published them under the title “Bulbuli gulshani Navoiy.” The works of Alisher Navoiy began to be taught in schools and madrasas starting from the Yarkand Khanate period, and his ghazals enriched navoiykhonlik (Navoi recitation gatherings). For this reason, in the 18th century, a dictionary of Navoi’s works was compiled in Kashgar. In particular, Nazariy, a devoted admirer of the great thinker, prepared and distributed a textbook titled “Navoi” in 1806 (Usmon., 2001:248). The poet Saburiy, in 1840, wrote a work titled “On Navoi’s Justice,” in which he reflected on the social and ideological aspects of Navoi’s epic “Saddi Iskandariy.”

In this regard, the Swedish scholar Sven Hedin, who traveled extensively in Central Asia and explored both the southern and northern slopes of the Tien Shan in the early 20th century, wrote: “Navoi is an exceptionally beloved author among readers here. As an example, one can point to the diverse works of Navoi preserved among the Uyghurs living in those regions. Even in the remote area of Lop Nor in Xinjiang, Navoi’s poems are sung and recited, and his epics are widely spread among ordinary people in the form of storytelling.”

Writers and poets from Xinjiang also actively participated in the unique cultural environment formed in the Kokand Khanate. The peak of Kokand’s literary environment coincided with the reign of Amir Umarxon, during which several scholars from Xinjiang were among the poets living and creating in the Khanate. In the work “Majmuat ush-shuaro” by Fazliy Namangani, who was known as the “Malik ush-shuaro” (King of Poets) of his time, one of the poets mentioned is Hislat Kashgari. He was born and raised in Kashgar and studied at one of its madrasas. In 1809, he moved to Kokand, settled in the Kataghan district, and continued his literary activity there (Jalilov., 2004:64).

His works, including the divan “Hadiya-i Hislat,” the famous ghazal with the radif “O‘ynamoq,” the fable “The Fight between the Mouse and the Cat,” and qasidas dedicated to his Kokand intellectual friends Hamadonikhon, Mir Haydarjon, Ishoqjon, G‘ulomjon, and Ma’sudjon, have survived to the present day.

After the defeat of the Jahongir Khoja uprising of 1826–1828, many people from Xinjiang fled to the Kokand Khanate, among whom was the Uyghur poet Hushhol Gharibiy (Hushhol Gharibiy., 2005:4). He had studied at the Qur’an school of Mawlavi Khoja Muhammad Okhun in Kashgar and later taught in a madrasa. As a participant in the uprising, the poet described the situation as follows:

“Day by day, oppression and injustice increased in our city, and many unlawful acts emerged. Peace was destroyed, calamities and hardships multiplied. Many upheavals occurred, Muslims fought against the infidels and put them in difficulty. But in the end, the unbelievers prevailed, and Muslims faced immense suffering and countless afflictions” (Hushhol Gharibiy., 2005:4).

Hushhol Gharibiy also lived in the Khanate when the Emir of Bukhara, Nasrullo, conquered Kokand in 1842. As a result of wars and the brutal suppression of uprisings, the devastated Fergana

Valley resembled a place of misery, and together with the local population, Gharibiy experienced severe hardship. In his work, he wrote: “As a result of my fate, in the path of purpose my name Hushhol turned into ‘Gharibiy’ (stranger). In the severity of separation and longing, estrangement in the path of desire became complete” (Jalilov., 2004:65).

Thus, Hushhol was his given name, while Gharibiy was his pen name. Much information about him can be found in the manuscript “Kulliyoti Gharibiy.” This Turkic-language work was written in 1845. Through his poetry, Gharibiy secured a достойное place in the literary environment of the Khanate.

Writers from the Kokand Khanate also lived and engaged in literary activity in Xinjiang. One such figure is mentioned by Imam Ali Kunduzī in his work “Tavorikhi manzuma.” While providing information about intellectuals who migrated from the Kokand Khanate to Xinjiang, he writes: “Muhammad Niyoz Okhund was one of the distinguished scholars and leading figures of this land. In poetry, he composed ghazals under the pen name Niyozī,” and notes that he was buried in Khotan in AH 1270 (1853–1854). Although the author refers to him as “Yarkandiy,” Polatjon Domulla Qayumiy, citing excerpts from his poetry, emphasizes that Niyozī was originally from Kokand. In one poetic fragment, Muhammad Niyoz Okhund states: “My father was Khudoyberdi Sufi, and my native place is Kokand. I have relatives near the bridge, in front of the mosque” (Qayumiy., 1998:180).

Not only poets and writers but also physicians moved between the two regions. One of them was Hasan Khoja, a physician from Andijan, who came to Kashgar in 1854–1855 with his assistants to combat the widespread smallpox epidemic among the population of Xinjiang. However, according to Imam Ali Kunduzī, he was captured and imprisoned by the Manchu authorities.

After Central Asia was conquered by Russia, the changes that took place in the Bukhara and Kokand Khanates were not uniformly accepted by the local population. Political instability and internal conflicts forced many representatives of cultural life into exile and migration. Especially after the capture of Tashkent, former officials of the Kokand Khanate, craftsmen, scholars, and intellectuals moved to Xinjiang. There, within the state established by Muhammad Yaqubbek, they contributed to the formation and development of centers of cultural life.

Under the leadership and support of Muhammad Yaqubbek, as well as through the initiatives of local rulers, a distinctive literary environment emerged in cities such as Yarkand, Khotan, Turfan, and Kashgar. Translation and creative activities flourished. This patronage of intellectuals and continuity of cultural traditions resembled the literary and cultural centers that had developed in the Kokand Khanate.

This situation reflected a kind of revival and restoration of the cultural traditions of the Khanate in this region. During this period, numerous works on Islam, history, and literature were written in Xinjiang. Translation activity also intensified, leading to the formation of distinctive schools of translation. One such center developed in Khotan, where, under the patronage of the governor Azizshah, works such as “Salovati Mas‘udiy” and Imom G‘azzoliy’s “Kimyoyi saodat” were translated from Persian into Turkic (Uzbek). These translations, carried out by a scholar named Muhammad Iso, later spread widely among Turkic-speaking populations in both lithographic and manuscript forms (Muzaffarzoda., 2004:156–157).

Among those shaped by the Kokand literary environment, Akmal Toshkandiy (Abdullaev I., 2002:213–217), together with the poet Toib, as well as the Kokand poet Pisandiy (Qayumiy., 1998:538), visited Kashgar and Yarkand in 1866. He composed a historical work dedicated to the Kokand commander Mullo Alikulī. Zarif, originally from Tashkent, also held literary gatherings in Yarkand together with the poet Tajalliy. During this period in Xinjiang, figures such as Furqat, and

historians Imam Ali Kunduzī, Mirza Shams Bukhari, Muhammad Toyib Muhammad Amin ogli, Muhammad Umar Qori Umidiy Margilani (Muhammad Umar., 2007), and Ghiyosiddin Margilani were active in literary and scholarly work. They all played an active role in the socio-political and cultural life of Xinjiang.

Akmal Sayidahmadkhan ogli Toshkandiy, born in Tashkent in the 1830s and the son-in-law of Muhammad Yaqubbek, was a bilingual poet of the 19th century. Between 1865–1877, he served as Yaqubbek's personal secretary and as a judge (qazi) in Kashgar, contributing significantly to the development and stability of the city. After Yaqubbek's death, he returned to Tashkent and opened a school. The Uyghur historian Muso Sayromiy wrote about him: "Akmal Khan was a learned, just, and fair-minded person. True to his name, he was indeed perfect and accomplished" (Musu Sayromiy., 1905:885). Ghiyosiddin Margilani moved from Margilan to Kashgar in the early second half of the 19th century and maintained close relations with local literary figures. He became friends with progressive writers such as Nizomiddin and Nosim Kashgari, collaborating creatively with them. The result of this collaboration was his work "Badavlatnoma," which was jointly written by both Uyghur and Uzbek poets.

In 1830, Muhammad Karim, who migrated from Xinjiang and settled in Shahrixon of the Khanate, and his grandson Alikhon Mulla Okhun Oraziy also gained a place within the Kokand literary environment. He studied at the Dasturkhonchi madrasa in Shahrixon and was influenced by the poetry of prominent Kokand literary figures such as Zavqiy and Muqimiy.

The obtained results show that cultural relations between the Kokand Khanate and Xinjiang were not accidental but rather a natural and historical process. These relations:

- were strengthened through economic interactions along the Great Silk Road;
- were easily assimilated due to ethnic and linguistic proximity;
- were spiritually unified through Islamic civilization and Sufism.

In particular, literary relations reached a high level, indicating the formation of a unified cultural space across the two regions. The wide dissemination of the works of Alisher Navoiy in Xinjiang is a vivid example of this.

At the same time, cultural exchange was evident not only among the elite but also in the everyday life of ordinary people—through cuisine, clothing, housing, and music.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, such relations clearly demonstrate the growing spirit of kinship and friendship between the peoples of Central Asia—particularly the Kokand Khanate—and Xinjiang. These interactions should be regarded not as accidental, but as a natural historical phenomenon.

As a result of long-standing historical ties, the peoples of Xinjiang and the Kokand Khanate developed close similarities in customs, culture, language, and art.

Socio-political, ethno-demographic, and migration processes, as well as economic relations between the Kokand Khanate and Xinjiang, contributed to the steady development of cultural connections between their populations.

During this period, various branches of applied arts—such as architecture, engraving, blacksmithing, coppersmithing, pottery, and jewelry—experienced mutual exchange of techniques and styles. Artistic products known as "Kashgar-style" became widely common among the population of the Kokand Khanate.

Surviving artistic monuments—historical structures and material cultural objects that played an important role in everyday life—serve as clear evidence of these interactions. Elements such as

the “Kashgar-style chimney,” “Kashgar baldok,” “Kashgar-style rubab,” “Kashgar-style veranda,” as well as Chinese-style porcelain, carpets, and dishes like Uyghur laghman, manpar, and manti, are all products of these exchanges.

The scientific and literary relations between the Kokand Khanate and Xinjiang were extensive and complex. This is because the educational systems, religious-Sufi institutions, and literary environments of the two regions were highly similar, making it difficult to distinguish clear differences. At the same time, these relations were directly connected to socio-political and economic processes between the two regions.

Due to socio-political factors, scholars, thinkers, poets, and writers moved between the two regions. For example, figures such as Muhammad Siddiq Rushdiy, Hislat Kashgari, and Hushhol Gharibiy from Xinjiang created works in the Kokand Khanate, while Kokand figures such as Imam Ali Kunduzi, Zarif, Akmal Toshkandiy, Ghiyosiddin Umar Margilani, Pisandiy, Toib, and the physician Hasan Khoja continued their activities in Xinjiang. They maintained active scholarly and literary exchanges.

These literary connections contributed to the formation of literary environments in both regions. For instance, the literary milieu of Kokand was closely linked with that of Yarkand under the leadership of Khoja Okhun Arshiy, where figures such as Sheikh Zaliliy, Muhammad Siddiq Rushdiy, Muhammad Sodiq Kashgari, Nazariy, Hislat Kashgari, and Hushhol Gharibiy were active.

In the first half of the 19th century, under the leadership of the Kashgar governor Zuhuriddin Khoja, the literary environment of Kashgar was strongly influenced by Kokand writers and poets, including Boborahim Mashrab and Amir Umarxon.

The Kokand Khanate also functioned as a kind of cultural transmitter, spreading the cultural achievements of other Central Asian khanates to Xinjiang. Through the territory of the Khanate, not only economic developments but also advanced intellectual ideas formed over centuries in Central Asia and neighboring regions were transmitted. The classical works of poets such as Alisher Navoiy, along with scholarly and spiritual literature, reached Xinjiang.

On this basis, a number of scholars and writers emerged in Xinjiang, and the development of cultural life made a significant contribution to strengthening the material and spiritual connections between the two regions.

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